

Psycho-social Quandaries of Young EFL Speakers in Bangladesh

Ahmad Mahbub-ul-Alam*

Erandathie Suchintha Kiridena Damunupola**

Mohammad Ehsanul Islam Khan***

Abstract

Bangladesh needs to give the general populace a sound working knowledge of social English with special emphasis on speaking skill. In this information age, English is the most needed prerequisite for worldwide communication at present. It is an inclusive language. While learning the English language, today's youth cannot overlook the verbal aspects. To survive in the global village one must be able to speak the language and become competent user of social English. However speaking English as a foreign language is the most challenging area to master for adult learners. Therefore the study focuses on some of the quandaries tertiary learners face in learning and using oral English in Bangladesh, and also suggests some remedial action and recommendations with a view to improving the verbal skills in English so that Bangladeshi youths become better EFL speakers, which is their ultimate goal of learning this foreign language. The study mainly focuses on the university students of Bangladesh.

Keywords: Spoken English Quandaries, Tertiary Learners, Psycho-social Perspective, Remedial Action

Introduction

Language is a unique human phenomenon. In most parts of the world, communities use more than one language, which makes them bilingual or multilingual. Two languages cannot co-exist side by side with the same degree of importance; this automatically makes one more powerful than the other. Bangladesh is a developing third world country with a largely monolingual population. The national language is Bengali (or Bangla) which is an Indo-European language derived from Sanskrit. The English language, scarcely spoken, remains a foreign language with little application. The rapidly developing telecommunication and IT (Information Technology) sectors and multinational companies which are setting up factories and offices in Bangladesh, all require employees with a working knowledge of English.

When learning the English language, people cannot overlook the oral aspect. To survive in the global village one must be able to speak the language and become a competent user of social English. Yet speaking is the most challenging and difficult area for adults to master. Therefore this research will look at some of the problems adults face when they have to speak a language they have been learning since primary school.

*Assistant Professor, Department of English, Manarat International University, Bangladesh

**Visiting Instructor in English, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka

***Lecturer, Department of English, Royal University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

The study specifically focuses on a group of university students, as they represent the present-day, educated, young adults of this country. They are part of a generation learning the language from childhood. The research focuses on some common speaking problems these individuals face and then discuss why students who have been learning English for more than 12 years are unable to use it successfully for oral communication. Certain social and psychological factors which have contributed to this situation have been considered. The focus of this research is the psychosocial viewpoint, so the researchers have looked at teaching and learning approaches, attitudes that help or hinder speaking in English, the social conditions that discourage or promote oral use, etc. Finally, remedial measures and strategies that individuals can adopt to improve oral English skills have been suggested.

Objectives

This work aims at finding the need for spoken English and the reasons behind the inability to use it, even after learning the language for over a decade, in the rapidly developing urban context of Bangladesh. The researchers have also looked into the social and psychological factors that discourage EFL speaking in Bangladesh.

Background

English is a foreign language in Bangladesh. It is mainly used for communication with the outside world and as a functional language. Middle and lower class citizens do not need English to function in the monolingual society they live in, but if used it is only for business and/or education purposes and therefore limited to urban, industrial and commercial areas of the country. It is nevertheless a status symbol among the affluent upper class. In the urban upper class, English is a second language and is even spoken in some homes. These affluent families are in the habit of sending their children to English medium or International schools and later abroad for quality higher education in English. The youth who are aspiring to enter the private sector job market need English for career development and social mobility.

“Though the standard of English nationally in Bangladesh is not high, and English is still an urban, elite language, with independence, globalization, satellite television, FM radio, etc. Bangladesh is being exposed to English as never before” (BANGLAPEDIA Vol.3, pg 491). It is clear that the booming garments industry and the IT sector demand spoken English. In other words the economic activities that link Bangladesh with the rest of the world use English as the link language.

With the wide range of local products being exported to all parts of the world and the opening of many multinational and international companies in Bangladesh, the need for English has grown. If one intends to find employment in these sectors English is a must.

Methodology

This study focuses on spoken English language problems faced by adults. To make the study manageable, a cross section of adults between the ages of 18 and 27 years studying in a private university in Dhaka were selected. The spoken English language problems of the target group are believed to represent the common problems of adults in society at large. The larger part of the data collection was done through questionnaires distributed among the target group. Informal interviews and classroom observations have also contributed to the collection of data. Some questionnaires were distributed and completed among one hundred students of a private university were analyzed. This process took up to almost three weeks. The sample consisted of BA in English students, BBA students and a handful of MA in English students. The purpose for filling out questionnaires was explained to the participants and the confidentiality of the personal information was assured.

Literature Review and Discussion

Before preparing the research paper the researchers went through the critical articles published in different sources and several books and surveys. Research on English language problems faced by adults in Bangladesh is very scant. Some articles highlight the existing problems in policy making and teaching English in an EFL context. Research on problems faced by individuals when speaking in English is few and far between.

The researcher Sabrin Farooqui (2007) looked at improving oral proficiency among university students in Bangladesh. She identified three main problems related to students' skills in spoken English. The first problem is the students' limited vocabulary. Their speech is limited due to the lack of words to express themselves. Three out of five participants (university teachers) said that the students have a small vocabulary. They do better in reading and writing skills but do poorly in speaking. The second problem she identifies is students "feel shy and do not want to speak in front of the class." The reason for this is the Bangladeshi people are monolingual, and the learners do not have the need or the environment to use English outside the classroom. The following statement of one university student stands true for many: "Outside the classroom, whom will we practice with? With our friends? They will laugh. It is not possible to practice speaking English with family members either." The third problem is the education system of the country, which is responsible for the lack of courage in individuals to speak English. "Students do not have many chances to interact in English in schools. In many schools, teachers take English classes in Bangla." "In schools, students focus entirely on rote memorization up to higher secondary level of education. Creativity is not encouraged."

The newspaper article "*Failing the Lingua Franca*" by Mushfique Wadud (2009), discusses key issues in the field of teaching and learning English in Bangladesh. The author interviewed and quoted many individuals involved in policy making, teaching and learning English in Bangladesh. He begins referring to the education policy of 1972: after the independence in 1971, importance was given to Bengali medium education, many English textbooks were translated to Bengali, and the medium of instruction was changed from English to Bengali. This shift from English to Bengali is seen in the article as a vital cause of the current oral English problem in the country.

Further, according to the article, unqualified individuals to teach for low wages has given rise to a “severe shortage of skilled English teachers”. This in turn has resulted in “the poor state of English” across the country. According to this article “disinterest among students” is also a common problem in the English language classrooms in Bangladesh. Students do not find the subject matter, the teaching methods, the environment and the teachers stimulating. To secure the SSC certificate in Bangladesh, one needs to obtain a pass mark for English. Many students adopt the method of memorization as a survival tactic. Evidently even after memorization, many answer scripts contain meaningless sentences, erroneous grammar and spelling.

Statistics shows that in the 2009 SSC examination 304 students failed in Bengali, while a staggering 11460 failed to get a pass mark in English (Islam, 2008). Finally the author concludes: “As a result of the poor base formed during redundant years in school and subsequently in college, students cannot improve their knowledge of English at university level.” The overall education system is seen as one not encouraging the practical use of English; instead it is only a subject that one needs to obtain a pass mark. “... getting good grades in the instant examination rather than learning for the future is the main aim of today’s students and it is for this mentality that the students never improve their standard of English”. According to the opinions of many educationalists of the country, the whole education system of Bangladesh should be reformed, as he quotes: “we do not have any language policy and so students and teachers do not get any guidelines for teaching or learning English” (Islam, 2008). Thus the article illustrates the status of English in the country.

Much has been said and written on the topic of adopting the CLT approach in teaching English in Bangladesh, focusing mainly on the need to improve communicative competence in English. However the English language classrooms in Bangladesh have still not completely accepted the communicative approach even after a decade of its being introduced. Lack of skilled teachers is again the biggest barrier. Many call for teacher training and changing attitudes among teachers and learners, while others call for a return to the previously used Grammar Translation method. According to Sikandar Ali (2006), “the current communicative approach remains stubbornly silent as the previous grammar translation method.” His article “*Communicative Method of Teaching English: Does It Deliver?*” published in *The Daily Star* newspaper points out: “Lamentably, at no stage of our learning up to graduation level, is there any active oral use of English in the classroom either by the students or by the teachers themselves. Even the introduction of the communicative method makes no difference. There being no explicit dialogue making lessons, the act of speaking has been left to the whims of the teachers and the students. As usual in the classroom teacher keeps himself busy reading passages and providing translation in the mother tongue which is followed by solving some grammatical riddles. The pupils simply keep quiet, look at books and get through the lesson without learning anything. The mutual disinclination to speaking owes to the factor that speaking has nothing to do with passing the examination.”

Some authors recommend CLT as a suitable method for the times and needs of learners in Bangladesh. But most of them explore the question why CLT has not produced the positive, desired effects in Bangladesh. They wanted to say that the fault is not with Communicative English, but with the unacceptable teaching standard, lack of motivation and sincerity of students,

teachers, and administrators, and above all, a non-conducive English Language teaching environment in almost all schools and colleges of general standard. Altering existing education policies, providing teacher training and changing learner and teacher attitudes are all imperative requirements.

Quandaries Faced by EFL Speakers in Bangladesh

Bangladesh is not an ESL setting; therefore speakers do not have near native fluency. Nor is perfect grammar and pronunciation expected. In an ESL context mutual intelligibility is the main expectation. However, many believe, “if your English is not perfect you must not open your mouth.” Many learners believe that others will laugh at them/at a person who make(s) mistakes while speaking English. Observations conducted in the English language classrooms prove that students have no exposure to social English. The teachers, in most cases, are not in the habit of greeting students in English; rather greetings have always been exchanged in mother tongue. When students have personal queries, share jokes or personal experiences during classroom discussions they always switch to Bangla as they cannot express these sentiments in English.

During the survey work communication was made in simple content words in English in order to be understood well by the students. As social English consists mostly of content words, grammatical mistakes of the students have not been detected. However mispronunciation was very common and it has often been found affecting the meaning of what was being said. The influence of mother tongue, especially of dialects is one reason for mispronunciation. Certain English sounds like /f/ are absent in Bangla while some subtle sounds in Bangla have no equivalent in English. Frequently mispronounced English sounds are /z/, /s/, /v/.

A list comprising some of the main (hypothetical) spoken English problems was presented to the participants for the question “What are the problems you have while speaking in English?” The following table shows the number of individuals who identified themselves as having one or more of the same.

Identified Problem(s)	No.	%
I don't have enough words to tell what I want	65	76
I make a lot of mistakes while speaking	40	47
My pronunciation is not good	36	42
I feel shy to speak in English	49	58
I take a long time to say what I want to say	63	74

Table-1: Identified Learner Problems

Figure-1: Identified Learner Problems

Lack of words to express themselves in English was a problem faced by over 75% of the target group. The inability to formulate thought into word too had a similar high percentage. Here the

lack of vocabulary and lack of practice in translating Bangla thoughts into English words is evident. According to an English language course teacher in the university shyness is ‘the most common problem’ among students. 58% of the respondents admitted that they too face this problem.

Apart from the above, individuals had the opportunity to state any other obstacles they had. The following is a list compiled of their statements.

Table-2: Obstacles Faced by Students

Barriers Faced by Students	
1.	There is no proper environment to speak English.
2.	I don't get a proper response from my listeners.
3.	I feel confused when I try to speak in English.
4.	I have grammatical problems so I get confused which is the correct form.
5.	Many people are not eager to speak English.
6.	I find it difficult to translate from Bangla to English.
7.	I can't understand the speakers' words. (pronunciation)
8.	I feel nervous when I speak in English.
9.	I don't know how to pronounce certain words in English.
10.	I don't have anyone to practice speaking.
11.	I like to talk in English but I'm scared to.

The statements in Table-2 prove that these individuals have the ability to express themselves in written English. These young adults have the desire and the knowledge about the language yet they do not have a supportive and stimulating environment. The frustration which results from an unaccommodating environment is evident in their words.

Remedial Action

The respondents are clearly aware of the need for English in a global society and are keenly aware of their limited oral skills. Although this awareness is present, very few are taking practical steps to improve their oral proficiency. Although 78% said they are taking steps to improve their oral skills, the question remains, how effective are these steps?

Table-3: Action Taken or Not to Improve Oral Skills

Taking any Action	No.	%
Yes	66	78
No	19	22
Total	85	100

Figure-2: Action Taken or Not to Improve Oral Skills

Figure-2 indicates that the majority or more than 75% of them are doing something to improve their oral skills.

Table-4 gives a list of the remedial actions.

Remedial Action(s)	No. of Individuals
1. Read English newspapers	22
2. Practice conversing in English	16
3. Read English novels	13
4. Watch English films	15
5. Listening to English news/BBC news	06
6. Listening to lectures/ teacher's expressions	02
7. Following the IELTS course	02
8. Following a spoken English course	01
9. Try to learn grammar	01
10. Try to learn new words/expressions	01
11. Reading aloud	01

Table-4: Remedial Action(s) Taken by Learners

The list proves that many individuals have no outside assistance to improve their oral English skills. They themselves have to address this issue and act on their own if they need to improve.

The most commonly used remedial action is reading newspapers or novels. 35 respondents believe that it will help them improve their English. Question remains: "How effective is silent reading as a strategy to improve oral skills?" Reading does help improve one's vocabulary and grammar but to improve oral skills something more aggressive and effective should be done by adults. Activities that focus more on listening and speaking skills should be incorporated.

The findings of this study revealed some key problems faced by adults when they have to speak in English, consequently providing valuable psychological and sociological insights on the topic of oral English in Bangladesh. It also raised a few important questions like what kind of remedial action should be taken by individual to improve their oral English skills.

Comments on the Findings

The research findings show how individuals are struggling with oral English proficiency. Not only is it evident within the target group but throughout urban Bangladesh. Although English has been taught as a compulsory subject in primary and secondary levels in Bangladesh, it has not had the desired impact on learners in terms of oral competence. Public exam results are not accurate measures of English language proficiency. The majority of school children reach tertiary level with or without a sound knowledge of grammar and almost no oral skills.

The target group has been learning English from primary school. Though for more than 12 years they have invested time and energy in learning a language, they still have very little confidence to speak in it. At the university some of these students are studying for their BA in English language, some for their MA in English language, others are studying for their degree in the medium of English. On close scrutiny, these students do not possess good oral skill. Unless a situation demands they do not speak in English. Teachers make it compulsory for students to speak in English during their language classes in a desperate attempt at the last level of formal education to make graduates competent speakers.

This study reveals that most of the individuals do not focus on speaking skills while learning English during their school careers. The approach to teaching and learning English in the school system still largely remain the Grammar Translation Method (GTM). English for many is only a written language which they have to learn to read and write without mistakes. Memorization has become the easiest and most successful learning method adopted by a large number of desperate young learners whose only goal is to pass the exam. This unknowingly hampers communication and makes learners timid speakers in later life.

Grammatical Accuracy Phobia

When called to speak in English, the biggest worry for many is grammatical accuracy. Fear of making mistakes or saying something wrong prevents most adult learners from speaking. Anxiety, when called to speak in English, makes learners nervous and more prone to failure. Many are generally slow in giving responses or they do not respond at all. If they attempt to make verbal responses of considerable length, these are marked with stammering, stuttering and lengthy pauses.

According to Johnstone (1994), “the child’s motivation to learn the second language is greatly dependent on the social context and the availability of authentic target language input and

opportunities to communicate.” Only a handful of children are fortunate to find such a learning Environment in Bangladesh. As a result they become poor English speakers in later life.

Bangladesh is largely monolingual; English is not required on a daily basis. It is frequently used only within upper class urban circles where affluent groups have foreign connections. English is neither a second language nor an official language in Bangladesh. It is a foreign language the general citizens read and write but hardly ever hear or speak. Hence the struggle with the use of oral English arises as many have no skill or practice in using English in a natural setting. The only opportunity for many individuals to hear or speak English is within the academic institution. This is not supportive to acquisition and learning of English for life. Since the spoken word is hardly heard in an informal social setting, learners are not accustomed to functional English. As a result there arises a host of problems.

Many a time individuals are at a loss for words to express themselves in English. In the researchers’ experience, people hardly ever initiate or maintain a conversation in English. The mother tongue, punctuated with English words is sufficient for communication. Many will prefer to remain silent even if they wish to express their ideas because they have no confidence to converse in English. Limitation in vocabulary hinders individuals from free expression. Speakers were always short of words to express their ideas and emotions because they have not been using English for these functions. Even when adults do speak in English, they mainly use content words to get the message across. Although they have been learning grammar for 12 years or more, there is a marked absence of articles, prepositions, adverbs, etc. in their speech.

Second language learners often produce errors of ‘syntax’ and ‘pronunciation’ thought to be resulted from the influence of their L1 (first language / mother tongue). This is known as “mother tongue interference”. English is a language of Germanic origin, while Bangla is of Indo-European origin. To begin with, there are many structural differences between the two languages. For example English follows the SVO (Subject + Verb + Object) order while Bangla the SOV (Subject + Object + Verb) order. Such differences are problematic to the learners of a second language. Many grammatical mistakes in speech occur due to this. Since speakers think in Bangla and try to speak in English, nine out of ten get their structure wrong and the correct message/meaning is not conveyed. For them the creative use of language, expressing ideas and emotions, talking about abstract concepts become impossible.

Pronunciation and Accentuation Phobia

Pronunciation of these learners is influenced by their L1. Pronunciation is important for both listening and speaking. When learners are not exposed early-on or often enough to the spoken word, they find it difficult to articulate the sounds of a foreign language. Bangla language has many dialects and sounds. Some of these sounds have no equivalents in English. The speakers who have been speaking Bangla from childhood have automatically trained their vocal track for these sounds. Adults trying to make new sounds of another language find it unattainable and their pronunciation becomes hazy. Many adults are unable to distinguish the difference between

sounds they hear in a foreign language and therefore are unable to produce them. What they do is produce a similar or the closest sound they know from their L1. If individuals spoke English since childhood or since they started learning it at primary level, this problem would not be present in adulthood.

The native speakers of English have both Linguistic competencies and Sociolinguistic competencies, says Johnston (1994). By Sociolinguistic competencies, Johnstone means mastery of the linguistic, cognitive, affective and socio-cultural meanings. For the foreign language learners, these are nearly impossible aspects to comprehend. In the context of Bangladesh where there is hardly any exposure to authentic language in real life settings, learners become confused and agitated by jokes, sarcasm, idiomatic use, social clichés and culture specific expressions. They do not understand these and do not know how to respond to them. Even the basics like turn-taking, negotiating, greeting, using polite expressions are greatly lacking.

Nervousness, shyness, fear and anxiety are all common feelings when one has to speak in English. One or a combination of these is felt in varying degree by all individuals when called upon to speak in English. As individuals are not accustomed to hearing themselves speaking in the foreign tongue, they cannot make the attempt without these ill feelings. Reluctance, hesitation and lack of confidence are therefore ever present.

Certain negative attitudes about the English language prevail and act as psychological barriers. For example many believe English is a difficult language to speak. This can be due to a couple of reasons: firstly, if learning English was not a pleasant experience, the language becomes hateful and learners do not wish to practice or try their tongue at it even now; secondly, if the learning environment does not encourage speaking or if the learners do not have the scopes for using oral English for the better part of their life, attempting it now makes them self-conscious. Lack of self-confidence, believing one cannot speak good English, or fear of being ridiculed, are key reasons why many adults fail as speakers. Negative attitudes act like barriers, preventing learners from speaking.

Beliefs and prejudices have a strong hold on individuals and are very difficult to shake off. One such belief is speech should be error-free at all times. Human beings are prone to make mistakes; slip of the tongue occurs even while speaking one's L1. So why should errors in a second language be unacceptable? In many countries around the world where English is not the native language, mutual intelligibility is the learners' goal; not near native fluency. While speaking, a person is constantly thinking and shaping thoughts into words; in this process changing words and restating, repeating, rephrasing, correcting, etc. take place. These are the characteristics of informal speech and learners should realize these and practice them.

“A second language is any language other than the first, or native, language learned; it is typically used because of geographical or social reasons. The term is to be distinguished from foreign language; linguist Eric Lenneberg uses second language in his critical period hypothesis to mean a language consciously learned or used by its speaker after puberty. In most cases, people never

achieve the same level of fluency and comprehension in their second languages as in their first language.” (Hasan, 2011)

As English is a status symbol in urban societies, many had the impression that others will laugh, ridicule and look down upon those who speak erroneous English. Hence individuals who has less or no confidence in their oral skills, prefer to avoid speaking in English at all.

People in urban circles also seem to have a high regard for those who speak with a British or American accent. This is another example, how beliefs and prejudices work among the people and within the society at large. Asians might feel that the British and the Americans are pronouncing English correctly as it is the L1 to them. It could also be a result of popular culture transmitted through music, television and movies, making the youth eager to imitate the West. Or, it could be that, the individuals who speak with such an accent in Bangladesh are the products of western education; they are the idols of the society.

It is not clear whether people even recognize the difference between the British and American English. Yet many aspire to have a British or an American accent as it is a status symbol. The British and American English are considered highly prestigious varieties. But no particular variety of English is intrinsically better or worse than other varieties. Learners should be made aware of this to free them from bias.

Difference in Educational Opportunities

Disparity in educational opportunities within the country is responsible for the poor standards of oral English nationwide. The younger generation, specifically the undergraduates are clearly aware of the importance of English. They know that spoken English will increase their self worth and employability in the global village. An individual will get limited or no assistance at all from society and institutions to improve their oral English skills. So it is in the hands of each individual to make a conscious effort to speak English in order to learn English. The majority of interviewed students who are going out into the society very soon said that their spoken English ability level is average. This awareness itself should drive them to take the initiative to improve their oral skill.

By looking through the list of remedial actions taken by individuals of the target group, one can say that they have no guidance and support from their environment to improve their English. Improving oral skill is an up-hill fight for many and each one is fighting alone. It is sad to see that due to lack of proper guidance, effective remedial action is not taken by learners. For example, a large part of remedial action taken to improve oral skills is focused on input rather than output. Silent readings, listening to news, watching movies etc are the steps in the right direction but a more aggressive and effective approach should be adopted by adults at this stage of their life to overcome their fear and introversion.

Recommendations and Limitations

To improve the spoken English skill of the young learners of Bangladesh, we should have a broad outlook towards the mistakes of the learners with a view to providing them a stress-free environment to practice English, thus leading to a gradual achievement of error-free oral English habit. The learners are needed to be kept engaged in continuous spoken English practice on a daily basis starting with some very common expressions of day-to-day life to get them accustomed in a natural practice of English speaking. Institutional support should be provided so that the learners can create an English speaking community as their practice field for enhancing their English speaking skill. Institutional practice of using drama can be introduced as a matrix for continued language development and refinement. (The World Factbook, 2011) Use of world-wide-web and mobile phones has to be maintained with a positive mode (e.g., BBC Janala) as these are very familiar tools among the young generation.

The research is however not without its limitations. The participants answered the questions provided by the researchers in the English language classroom, at the end of a lesson, and in some cases in the presence of their English teacher. Hence answers could have been biased. Some answers might have been influenced by a preceding negative or positive learning experience.

Conclusion

Any language used by a person is first and foremost a personal expression. Secondly, it is a social and cultural phenomenon. English, the language of the British, will never be equal to an Asian's first language. It is a foreign language from a foreign culture, yet due to its global value it has become essential. Due to this foreignness, speakers in the East will continuously encounter quandaries in pronunciation, syntax, grammar and vocabulary. The focus of this study has been the oral language predicaments faced by a group of young university students in Bangladesh, for whom English is a foreign language. The most common quandaries like lack of words to express one's self, fear, shyness, anxiety are not limited to individuals of the target group alone, rather many individuals living in the urban Bangladesh face similar problems when they have to speak English.

The common widespread spoken English language predicaments among the youth call for effective action by one and all. Everyone's secret desire to speak in good English can be fulfilled if all come together to create an environment supportive of oral English. To be able to speak well in a foreign language requires many other inputs besides classroom teaching. It requires commitment, confidence and continued practice in real life situations. Without these three things accomplishments are hard to come by. A language develops and gains refinement only on its usage. Language is constantly changing and growing; so acquiring oral skills too should be a continuous process. The findings of the present study are believed to help individuals to gain confidence to practice their speaking skill, be it at school, at work, at higher educational institutions or in friendly circles. Thereby, creating a learning environment which encourages spoken English, accepts it as a natural, necessary part of the 21st century urban life. Making people conscious and active will hopefully pave the way to an English speaking future generation in Bangladesh.

Bibliography

Ali, Sikandar. (2006), Newspaper Article: *Communicative method of teaching English: Does it deliver?* *The Daily Star*, 1st July 2006. Web. Information retrieved from: <http://www.thedailystar.net/2006/07/01/d60701020528.htm>

Farooqui, Sabrin. (2007), *Developing Speaking Skills of Adult Learners in Private Universities in Bangladesh: Problems and Solutions*. Australian Journal of Adult Learning, Volume: 47, Number: 1, Issue: April 2007.

Hasan, S M Mehdi, (2011), Online Article: *Condition of English in Bangladesh: Second Language or Foreign Language*. Web. August 31, 2014 Information retrieved from. <<http://forum.daffodilvarsity.edu.bd/index.php?topic=4122.0>>.

Hudson, R A. *Sociolinguistics*. N.p.: Cambridge university press, 1980. Print.

Islam, Sirajul. Ed, *Banglapedia* Vol.3. Bangladesh 2008. Print.

Johnstone, R. *Teaching Modern Languages at Primary School*: The Scottish Council for Research Education, 1994. Print.

Wadud, Mushfique, (2009), *Failing the Lingua Franca*. *NEW AGE Xtra* 24 July 2009: 12-19. Print.

CIA-The World Factbook, May-2011

BANGLAPEDIA

Appendix

Questionnaire

Class.....
 Age..... Sex M/F

Please answer all the questions. use Bangla language if you need to

1. At what age did you start learning English: Before 6 yrs. 6-12 yrs. 12-20 yrs. After 20 yrs.
2. Did you enjoy learning English in school? Always Sometimes Never
3. When learning, did you ever get time to speak in English? Yes No
4. How do you see your level of spoken English now? Poor Average Good
5. Which of the following do you do? (can mark more than one)
 Listen to English music Watch English films Watch English news Watch the cricket world cup
 Read English stories/ comics Read English newspapers Access Internet and Face book
6. Do you have to speak in English for any of your daily activities? Yes No
 If yes for what
7. With whom do you speak in English?

- 8. Does your family support you in learning to speak English? Always Sometimes Never
- 9. Is English a difficult language to speak? Yes No
- 10. Are you doing anything to improve your spoken English? Yes No

If yes what.....

- 11. What are the problems you have when speaking in English? (mark more than one)

I don't have enough words to tell what I want I make a lot of mistakes while speaking
 My pronunciation is not good I feel shy to speak in English
 I take a long time to say what I want to say

Write any other problems you have when speaking in English:

.....

- 12. Will people around you laugh if you make mistakes when speaking in English? Yes No
- 13. Is it good to have a British or American accent when speaking English? Yes No
- 14. The English language is not our language so it is:
 A nuisance A necessary evil Useful for us Today we can't live without it

- 15. Why do young people like you in Bangladesh need to learn spoken English? What benefits await you?

.....

